

GROWTH STRATEGY ADOPTION AND PERFORMANCE OF SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES IN ENUGU STATE, NIGERIA

Onyia, Nnamdi Charles, Prof. N.M Ile and Onyema, Chidozie Nwabueze

Department of Business Administration Enugu State University of Science and Technology

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15441352>

Abstract: The study investigated the effect of growth strategy adoption on performance of small and medium enterprises in Enugu State, Nigeria. The specific objectives include; ascertain the effect of market penetration strategy on sales growth of small and medium enterprises in Enugu State, Nigeria and determine the effect of product development strategy on product-oriented innovativeness of small and medium enterprises in Enugu State, Nigeria. The study used survey research design. The population of the study was one thousand four hundred and seven (1,407) registered small and medium scale enterprises. The sample size of the study was 150 respondents. Instrument used for data collection was the questionnaire. The reliability coefficient of instrument was 0.78 and this was measured using Cronbach's alpha coefficient which showed consistency of the instrument. T-test tool was used in testing the hypotheses. Findings revealed that market penetration had a significant positive effect on sales growth of SMEs in Enugu State, Nigeria ($t = 87.695$, $pv .000 < 0.05$ level significant) and product development strategy had a significant positive effect on product-oriented innovativeness of SMEs in Enugu State, Nigeria ($t = 79.401$, $pv .000 < 0.05$ level of significant). The study concluded that growth strategy adoption had a significant positive effect on performance of SMEs in Enugu State, Nigeria. Based on the findings and conclusion reached, the study recommended that that management of Aqua Rapha should also embark on serious exercise, training and development of personnel on market penetration strategy as tools to increase sales growth in an organization and Aqua Rapha should foster product development strategy as a culture within firm experimentation in order to encourage employees to explore new ideas and approaches, they involve some level of uncertainty. Create incentives for innovation and recognize and reward employees who contribute innovative solutions.

Keywords: Growth Strategy Adoption, Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Historically, Nigeria's independence in 1960 marked a turning point in the growth and development of SMEs, which has created much of the emphasis on SMEs as panacea in the reduction of poverty and joblessness or unemployment in Nigeria as a whole. The adoption of the Economic Reform Programme (ERP) of 1986 indicated a pivotal shift from impressive, capital intensive and large scale industrial projects based on import substitution to small scale industries with enormous potentials for the development of domestic linkages for sustainable economic and industrial development (Agwu & Emeti, 2024). As such, SMEs perform very important part of the Nigerian economy (Eniola & Ektebang, 2024). Though, SMEs have developed over the

years through many agencies in Nigeria in spite of its challenges such as the National Directorate of Employment (NDE), Skill Acquisition Centre and Industrial Development Centres.

The growth of Small Medium and Scale Enterprises (SMEs) is becoming a crucial component of any country's economy, especially in Nigeria because of its contribution to employment creation, lessening poverty and viable development (Beynon 2020). Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) play a major role in most economies, particularly in developing countries. Small Medium and Scale Enterprises (SMEs) account for the majority of businesses worldwide and are important contributors to global economic development. They represent about 90% of businesses and more than 50% of employment worldwide. Formal Small Medium and Scale Enterprises (SMEs) contribute up to 40% of national income (GDP) in emerging economies. These numbers are significantly higher when informal Small Medium and Scale Enterprises (SMEs) are included. According to our estimates, 600 million jobs will be needed by 2030 to absorb the growing global workforce, which makes SME development a high priority for many governments around the world (Munjeyi, 2017).

Small Medium and Scale Enterprises (SMEs) have been accepted worldwide as instruments of economic growth and development. Governments, particularly in the developing countries, have made tremendous efforts and established policies towards enhancing the capacity and sustainability of Small Medium and Scale Enterprises (SMEs). However, despite government institutional and policy support, there is a grave concern and scepticism about whether Small Medium and Scale Enterprises (SMEs) can bring about economic growth and development, particularly in developing countries. In Nigeria, there have been a series of government interventions to boost the activities of Small Medium and Scale Enterprises (SMEs) through the establishment of agencies and programmes to provide consultancy, information, and guidelines to Nigerians who establish and own businesses (Nkiruka & Ogundeinde, 2016). They continued by saying that some of these programmes include: Small and Medium Enterprise Equity Investment Scheme (SMEEIS) established in 2001 and the Small and Medium Scale Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN) established in 2003.

Performance has been defined generally in the economics viewpoint of social performance, comprising dimensions such as distributed to competency (profitability), industrial efficiency (cost reduction), and innovativeness (advancement). Conduct was the firm's choice of crucial decision variables such as price, advertising, capacity, and quality (Wang, Dou, Zhu, & Zhou, 2022). Thus, in policy terms, conduct could be viewed as the economic dimensions of firm strategy (Porter, 1981). Performance is a fundamental belief in management studies. Managers are assessed based on their firm performance. Effective performance influences the firm to improve maintenance. Firm achievement is demonstrated in managing competitiveness or progress of competitive status that proves superior and justifiable business performance (Sidi, Haim & Manaf, 2020).

Actually to achieve greater performance, firms must have to adopt growth strategic positions that will persistently give them the strength to maintain their market. Thus, management must focus their attention on structuring their businesses to be customer focused and practical to industry competitors (Uchegbulam, Akinyele, & Ibidunni, 2022). Based on backdrop, the study seeks to examine the effect of growth strategy adoption on performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The importance of SMEs in an economy cannot be under estimated. In fact, world governments, policy makers whether in developed or developing countries now see SMEs are as sources of employment, wealth creation and innovation. The SMEs produced a wide range of products to meet domestic and global demand. It operated in diverse business areas and created employment opportunities within the country (Ghose, 2021).

In spite of various growth strategies most Small Medium and Scale Enterprises (SMEs) adopt in the track of their operations, their growth is still limited and they have not performed credibly well. This has resulted due to high attracted talented team workers, decline of sales volume, difficulty to penetrate new market, low product development and unfavourable business environment arising from hostile legal requirements, high taxes, inflation, fluctuating and unreliable exchange rates, all making it difficult to make significant profits to survive which most Small Medium and Scale Enterprises (SMEs) needed to work heard in order to over such issues since their competitors move strongly every day by day. The study therefore sought to ascertain the effect of growth strategy adoption on performance of SMEs in Enugu State of Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to examine the effect of growth strategy adoption on performance of small and medium enterprises in Enugu State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to;

- i. Ascertain the effect of market penetration strategy on sales growth of small and medium enterprises in Enugu State, Nigeria.
- ii. Determine the effect of product development strategy on product-oriented innovativeness of small and medium enterprises in Enugu State, Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Growth

Growth is sometimes used to designate all the quantitative changes brought about in the structure and functions of the human anatomy and physiology. Growth as a process is an irreversible increase in size which involves a synthesis of the protoplasm (Obunike & Udu, 2018). It refers to an increase, expansion or change over time. Small scale manufacturing firms' growth has been identified as a key driver for the creation of wealth and employment and economic development in every country (Obunike & Udu, 2018).

Strategy

Strategy can be defined as the match between an organization's resources and skills and the environmental opportunities as well as the risks it faces and the purposes it wishes to accomplish (David, 2023). Quinn, Mintzberg and James (2019) also defined strategy as a pattern or a plan that integrates organization's major goals, policies and actions into a cohesive whole (McKelvie & Wiklund, 2020).

Adoption

Adekoya and Tologbonse, (2021) adoption is regarded as a decision to make full use of an innovation or technology as the best course of action available. Adoption of an organization is the decision made by an individual or group to use an innovation.

Growth Strategy

Growth strategy refers to a strategic plan formulated and implemented for expanding firm's performance. Warugu (2021) noted that growth strategies provide opportunities for the business enterprise to respond to the various challenges within its operating environment (Quinn, Mintzberg & James, 2019).

Growth Strategy Adoption

Growth strategies are methods aimed at winning larger market share, even at the expense of short-term earnings. These involves diversification, product development, market penetration, innovation, branding and market development (Leithner & Guldenberg, 2020). In this study, growth strategies refer to strategies adopted by small and medium scale enterprises that allow them to expand and employ more people to improve their performance (Yusuf & Dansu, 2023; (Adeyemi & Aremu, 2021; Moriam, Mukaila & Hameedat, 2023; Kiptugen (2022).

Components of Growth Strategy Adoption

There are different growth strategies that can be adopted by firms. They include market penetration, market development, product development, diversification etc (Adeyemix & Aremu, 2021; Moriam, Mukai & Hameedat, 2023).

Market Penetration Strategy

Market penetration is a growth strategy, in which a firm tries to seek a higher volume of sales of present products by penetrating (or getting deeper), into existing markets. Market penetration strategy involves exploring new markets for company's products. For example, many companies have achieved remarkable growth by entering into foreign markets; pushing their products by changing size, packaging, and brand name (Porter, 1998; Grant, 2018; Mascarenas, 2016).

Product Development Strategy

Product development strategy refers to strategies the firm tries to grow by developing improved products for the present market. Porter (1998) the most suitable growth strategies for a small firm are those concerning product development and market development. Nooteboom (2019) suggests that SMEs pursue product innovation strategies in emerging markets and marketing innovation strategies in mature niche markets. Yogo (2023) also suggests that product development strategy is a very effective strategy in mature markets with products in late life cycle stages.

Performance

Alrowwad *et al* (2020) stated that organizational performance is the extent to which the organization is able to achieve the goals and objectives set in its strategy. As for Le and Lei (2019), it was found that the organizational performance refers to the organization's administrative and practical effectiveness of the mechanism of using its resources in the interest of the organization (employees and stakeholders). Organizational performance consists of several main dimensions, including performance axes of financial performance, operational efficiency, customer satisfaction, sales growth, product-oriented innovativeness, employee satisfaction, and awareness of social responsibility (Arundel, *et al*, 2019; Wang, 2019; Singh *et al*, 2021).

Small and Medium-Scale Enterprises

In an attempt to separate small enterprises from medium enterprises, a Survey Report on MSMEs in Nigeria (2012) defines small enterprises as those enterprises whose total asset excluding land and building are above 5 Million Naira but not exceeding 50 Million Naira with total workforce of above 10 but not exceeding 49 employees. While the medium enterprises are those enterprises whose total asset excluding land and building are above 50 Million Naira but not exceeding 500 Million Naira with a total workforce of between 50 and 199 employees. The researcher adopted definition of SMEs by MSMEs in Nigeria (2012).

Performance Indicators of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs)

Performance is measured using diverse parameters by different organizations some firms measure it through expansion, sales growth, product orientation innovation, survival, number of employees and capital employed. According to Hornsby (2020) performance is described as an action or achievement considered in relation to how successful it is. Prior to the 1980s financial indicators were the sole measurement rods of performance such as profit, return on investment, sales per employee and productivity (Ojuye & Egberi, 2018; Kouser, Bano, & Azeem, 2022; (Delmar, McKelvie, & Wennberg, 2023; Obunike & Udu, 2018).

Theoretical Framework

This study adopted the business growth theory. The business growth theory was propounded by Penrose (1959). The theory offers strong principles governing the growth of firms and the rate at which firms can grow successfully. She claimed that there are a bundle of internal and external resources that help a firm to grow fast to realize competitive advantage. According to Penrose (1959), firm size is incidental to the growth process, whereas firm growth is determined by the environmental factors. Penrose has also suggested that ignorance of these factors results in failure and loss of competitive advantage. The theory further shows that firms' resources were only meaningful in the context of its environment. Penrose mostly used case histories to develop some theoretical principals and logics and are acknowledged that testing them remains problematic (Echdar & Si, 2013). Firms are institutions that are created by people to serve different purposes and they operate in a disequilibrium thereby seeking to maintain administrative coordination within a multi stakeholder environment. Managers are motivated by the struggle for firm performance and growth hence the need for achievement and recognition to generate both creative innovations and adaptive responses through new resource combinations (Kor, & Mahoney, 2000; Echdar, & Si, 2013).

Empirical Review

Reuben (2018) studied the influence of market penetration strategies on organisational growth in the steel industry in Kenya. The population of the study comprised of all steel industries and firms in the Kenya market. The study found that market penetration strategies influence organisational growth of firms in the steel industry. Adamu (2020) conducted a study on effect of market penetration on the performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Makurdi metropolis, Benue State, Nigeria. Multiple regression analysis was used as method of data analysis. Market segmentation, product packaging and product pricing all had a positive effect on performance of small and medium enterprises in Makurdi Metropolis, Benue State and the effect is statistically significant.

Bukoye and Muritala (2023) studied conceptual review on penetration strategy on the performance of manufacturing industry in North West Nigeria. This study, through examination of the multidimensionality of

penetration strategy and performance from the existing entrants' literature, and it is evident that the various penetration strategies are having a positive impact on the market and the calibre of performance in the organization.

Banabo and Ogbomah (2024) examined market penetration strategies and organizational growth in Nigeria. The aim is to increase organizational efforts through appropriate pricing in order to acquire a bigger market share than the organization's competitors seek. The study discovered that there is a positive and significant relationship between market penetration strategy and the growth of manufacturing organizations in Nigeria.

Zheng (2022) examined the innovation strategy of management concerning a number of small and medium-sized enterprises. The findings revealed that innovativeness did not only happen in high-tech industries, but also can be achieved in traditional low-tech sectors.

Kalay and Lynn (2023) investigated the impact of innovation strategy, organizational structure, innovation culture, technological capability and customer and supplier relationships, which appear in the literature as strategic innovation management practices in business enterprises, on firm innovation performance. The study revealed that, data collected from 132 managers at 66 firms operating in the manufacturing sector in the TRB2zone of Turkey were analyzed.

Orga (2023) examined innovation and sustainability of small and medium scale enterprises in Enugu Metropolis. The major objective of the study was to examine innovation and sustainability of SMEs. Methodology research design was used and population of the study was 300 made up of owners and workers and 35 SMEs. The researcher found out that product innovation had significant positive effect on the circular economy of small and medium enterprises in Enugu metropolis, with the statistical evidence.

Olughor (2024) investigated how innovation affects business performance in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in an up-and-coming market, like Nigeria. The study demonstrated that there is a high correlation among factors used to measure innovation. And secondly, innovation was found to influence business performance.

Cheng *et al* (2024) investigate inter-relationships among three types of eco-innovation (process, product, organizational) and their relative impact on business performance. Using structural equation modeling with 121 samples collected from Taiwan Environmental Management Association, the result finds out that eco-organizational innovation has the strongest effect on business performance.

Hervas-Oliver *et al* (2024) contributed to the study of process innovation as a growth strategy for SMEs, enriching and complementing the well-researched debate about product innovation. The results show that process innovation strategy is mainly shaped by the Acquisition of embodied knowledge, which acts as a key mechanism for countering firms' weak internal capabilities.

Gap in Empirical Literature

Although growth strategy adoption appears to be attracting attention in contemporary organizations in recent times, few researchers have investigated its relevance of growth strategy adoption. Partala, Jantunen, Kuukkanen and Merikoski (2024) found that intention to grow and level of networking with other companies and public actors were directly related to actualized growth. Odokoro, Uzuagu and Abanyam (2022) Findings also indicated that the strategies used by SMEs in implementing ES included ensuring that the business

activities do not affect the natural environment, reducing pollutants in the environment, implementing green manufacturing practices such as waste reduction, reuse and recycling, among others. This study sought to bridge these gaps.

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized descriptive research design. The descriptive design describes phenomena as they exist. It issued to identify and obtain information on the characteristics of a particular problem or issue. Therefore, the target population of this study included human resources officers, head of departments, director and staff members. Conveniently the study focused on Aqua Rapha Company with a total of one hundred and fifty (150) staff from the company internal record, 2024. Kothari, (2014) defines sample as small group of respondents drawn from a population about which a researcher is interested in getting the information so as to arrive at a conclusion. The study adopted entire 150 as sample size determination due to small nature of it. Random sampling technique was adopted with forded paper in a box thereafter a little child was asked to pick according paper contents inside the box and also allow respondents to put down their opinions in the questionnaire.

This in line with Kothari, (2014) and Sekaran (2018) that technique is used because it guarantees desired representation of the relevant sub groups confirm that sampling and favours cost, time and other resource. says that sampling. According to Kothari (2014), a questionnaire is a method of collecting data which uses a set of questions for collecting data. In this method data were collected with the help of questions. Through this method, selected respondents of this study had to answer questions on their own and bring back to the researcher. Structured questions were used in helping the researcher to get answers and relevant information from respondent. The questionnaire was made up of 5 points Likert scale namely strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree (SA-SD). Data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics were analyzed using frequencies, percentages and mean while inferential statistics t-test statistical tool was used to test the hypothesis.

Test of Hypotheses

Test of Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Market penetration strategy does not have significant positive effect on sales growth of small and medium enterprises in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Contingency table of the responses on market penetration strategy does not have significant positive effect on sales growth of small and medium enterprises in Enugu State, Nigeria.

(N =145)	SA	A	UD	D	SD
Market penetration serves as avenue of income generation.	100 (69%) 500	20 (14%) 80	10 (7%) 30	5 (3%) 10	10 (7%) 10
Market penetration boosts SMEs sales	100 (69%) 500	20 (14%) 80	10 (7%) 30	5 (3%) 10	10 (7%) 10

growth.					
---------	--	--	--	--	--

Source: Field Survey, 2025

In table 1 above analyzed effect of market penetration on sales growth in SMEs. Therefore, with evidence from the analysis, *t* statistic of 87.695 with probability value of .0000. **df:** The degrees of freedom for the test. For a one-sample *t* test, $df = n - 1$; so here, $df = 145 - 1 = 144$. **Decision Rule:** If the calculated *t*-value is greater than the critical *t*-value (i.e $t_{cal} > t_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly. **Result:** *t* critical =9.925, *t*-value of 87.695 and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms that the assertion confirms that there is significant positive effect of market penetration on sales growth of SMEs in Enugu State.

Test of Hypothesis Two

H02: Product development strategy does not have significant positive effect on product-oriented innovativeness of small and medium enterprises in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Contingency table of the responses on product development strategy does not have significant positive effect on product-oriented innovativeness of small and medium enterprises in Enugu State, Nigeria.

(N =145)	SA	A	UD	D	SD
Continuous product development keeps firms functioning.	100 (69%) 500	20 (14%) 80	10 (7%) 30	5 (3%) 10	10 (7%) 10
Product development drive from innovative system.	100 (69%) 500	20 (14%) 80	10 (7%) 30	5 (3%) 10	10 (7%) 10

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 2 One-Sample Test

	Test Value = 0					
	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
1. Continuous product development keeps firms functioning.	79.401	145	.000	4.16755	4.0643	4.2708
2. Product development drive from innovative system.	62.204	145	.000	3.98936	3.8633	4.1155

In table 2 above analyzed effect of product development strategy on product-oriented innovativeness in SMEs. Therefore, with evidence from the analysis, t statistic of 79.401 with probability value of .0000. **df:** The degrees of freedom for the test. For a one-sample t test, $df = n - 1$; so here, $df = 145 - 1 = 144$. **Decision Rule:** If the calculated t-value is greater than the critical t-value (i.e $t_{cal} > t_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly. **Result:** t critical =9.925, t-value of 79.401 and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000. This affirms that the assertion proves there is significant positive effect of product development strategy on product-oriented innovativeness of SMEs in Enugu State.

Summary of Findings

- i. Market penetration had a significant positive effect on sales growth of SMEs in Enugu State, Nigeria ($t = 87.695$, $pv .000 < 0.05$ level significant).
- ii. Product development strategy had a significant positive effect on product-oriented innovativeness of SMEs in Enugu State, Nigeria ($t = 79.401$, $pv .000 < 0.05$ level of significant).

Conclusion

In light of findings, the study concluded that growth strategy adoption had a significant positive effect on performance of SMEs in Enugu State, Nigeria. Meanwhile, the study also concludes that market penetration and product development strategies had a significant positive effect on sales growth and product-oriented in SMEs in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations were made;

- i. It was recommended that management of Aqua Rapha should also embark on serious exercise, training and development of personnel on market penetration strategy as tools to increase sales growth in an organization.
- ii. Aqua Rapha should foster product development strategy as a culture within firm experimentation in order to encourage employees to explore new ideas and approaches, even if they involve some level of uncertainty. Create incentives for innovation and recognize and reward employees who contribute innovative solutions.

Contributions to Knowledge

The study will contribute to the existing body of knowledge on growth strategy adoption and performance of SMEs in Enugu State. Specifically, the study will shed light on the effect of dependent and independent variables. The researcher contributed basically on model of growth strategy adoption and performance with statistical evidence which illustrated below;

References

- Adeyemi, N., & Ramanujam, V. (2021). Measurement of business performance in strategy research: A comparison of approaches. *The Academy of Management Review*, 11(4), 801- 814.
- Agwu, M. O & Emeti, C. I. (2024). Issues, challenges and prospects of small and medium scale enterprises (smes) in port-harcourt city, Nigeria. *European Journal of Sustainable Development*, 3(1), 101-114.
- Alrowwad, A. A., Abualoush, S. H., & Masa'deh, R. E. (2020). Innovation and intellectual capital as intermediary variables among transformational leadership, transactional leadership, and organizational performance. *Journal of Management Development*, 39(2), 196-222.
- Arundel, A., Bloch, C., & Ferguson, B. (2019). Advancing innovation in the public sector: Aligning innovation measurement with policy goals. *Research policy*, 48(3), 789-798
- Adamu, G. (2020). Effect of market penetration on the performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Makurdi metropolis, Benue State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Business, Management and Social Research*, 09(01), 508-515.
- Adekoya, A.E & Tologbons, E.B (2021). Adoption and diffusion of innovations. *Agricultural Extension Society in Nigeria*, 1(2), 36 – 47

- Banabo, E & Ogbomah, T (2024). Market penetration strategies and organizational growth in Nigeria manufacturing sector, *International Journal of Economics, commerce and management*, 12(2), 2-24
- Bukoye, J. A & Muritala, T. A. (2023). Conceptual review on penetration strategy on the performance of manufacturing industry in North West Nigeria. *Open Journal of Business and Management*,11(1), 1745-1756
- Best, J. W., & Kahn, J. R. (2021). *Research in education* (9th Edition). Prentice Hall of Inc. Private Limited
- Best, J.W., & Kahn, J. V (2006). *Research in education*. Hong Kong: Pearson Education Inc.
- Beynon M.J., Jones P & Pickernell D. (2020). SME development strategy and product development, *The International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation*, 21(1) 3–16
- Creswell, J. W (2005). *Research Design: A qualitative, quantitative and mixed method approaches*. London: Sage Publication Inc.
- Creswell, J.W (2015). Designing a mixed methods study in primary care. *The Annals of Family Medicine*, 2(1), 7-12.
- Cheng, C.C., Yang, C.I & Sheu, C. (2024). The link between eco-innovation and business performance: a Taiwanese industry context. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 64(1), 81-90.
- David, F. R. (2023). *Strategic Management: Concepts and Cases* (9th Edition). Pearson Education, Inc. Upper Saddle River, New Jersey.
- Delmar, F., McKelvie, A & Wennberg, W (2023). Untangling the relationships among growth, profitability and survival in new firms, *Technovation*, 33(8–9), 276–291.
- Echdar, H. S., & Si, M., S. (2013). The effects of internal and external environment on human capital development. empirical study on manufacturing company. Gupublik, Indonesia. *Journal of Business Management*, 1(2), 39-56
- Eniola, A., & Saffu, K. (2024). Planning and performance of small and medium enterprise operators in a country in transition, *Journal of Small Business Management*, 43 (4), pp. 480–497.
- Grant, R. M. (2018). *Contemporary Strategy Analysis* (Sixth). Blackwell Publishing.

- Heroas-diver, A., Yunfei, S., Appienti, W & Forkuoh, S. (2024). Product innovation and SMEs performance in the manufacturing sector of Ghana. *British Journal of Economics, Management & Trade*. 2(1), 78-90
- Hornby, A.S. (2020). *Oxford advanced learners dictionary*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Kock, I. B. (2021). Small and medium scale enterprises and employment generation in Nigeria: the role of finance. *Kuwait Chapter of Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 1(9), 79-93.
- Kor, Y. Y., & Mahoney, J.T. (2000). Penrose's resource-based approach: The process and product of research creativity. *Journal of Managerial Studies*, 37(1):109–139
- Kothari, C.R. (2014). *Research methodology: Methods and Techniques*. 2nd Edition, New Age International Publishers, New Delhi.
- Kouser, R., Bano, T & Azeem, M (2022). Inter-relationship between profitability, growth and size: A case of non-financial companies from Pakistan, *Pakistan Journal of Commerce and Social Sciences*, 6(2), 405–419
- Kalay, F & Lynn, G. (2023). The impact of strategic innovation management practices on firm innovation performance. *Research Journal of Business and Management*, 2(3), 412-429.
- Kiptugen, G. (2022). Strategic responses to a changing competitive environment. A case study of KCB, Unpublished MBA project, University of Nairobi
- Laithner, Tajudeen O. & Francis S. Dansu (2020). SMEs, business risks and sustainability in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Social Sciences* 2(9): 76–94.
- Le, P. B., & Lei, H. (2019). Determinants of innovation capability: the roles of transformational leadership, knowledge sharing and perceived organizational support. *Journal of knowledge management*. 1(2), 56-78
- Mascarenhas, K. S. (2016). Ethnic minority small and medium-sized enterprise in England: diversity and challenges, paper presented to the 51st conference of the International Council for Small Business, Melbourne, Australia 18-21 June
- McKelvie, A & Wiklund, J. (2020). Advancing firm growth research: a focus on growth mode instead of growth rate. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 34(2). 261–288.

- Moriam, G. & Eric P. (2023). A strategy to promote innovative small and medium enterprises. the world bank poverty reduction and economic management department. Latin America Finance and Private Sector Unit (February 2008) Policy Research Working Paper 4518
- Munjeyi E (2017). The impact of legal and regulatory framework on smes development: evidence from Zimbabwe, *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 8(20), 2-17
- Nkinika, N.I. (2016). Factors contributing to women being successful in the SMME sector. MBA dissertation. University of Johannesburg.
- Nooteboom, B. (2019). Innovation and diffusion in small firms: Theory and evidence. *Small Business Economics Journal* 6 (5), 327-347
- Ojuye, T.E & Egberi, O.E (2018). Determinants of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) performance in Delta State, Nigeria, *International Journal of Business & Law Research* 6(2), 59-70
- Olughor, R. J. (2024). Effect of innovation on the performance of SMEs organizations in Nigeria. *Management*, 5(3), 90–95.
- Orga, J.I (2023). Innovation and sustainability of small and medium scale enterprises in Enugu Metropolis, *CNAJ*, 29(4), 1-21
- Obunike, C.F & Udu, A.A (2018). Technological innovativeness and growth: a study of small scale manufacturing firms in Lagos
- Penrose, E. T. (1959). *The theory of the growth of the firm*. New York: Cambridge, MA 35.
- Porter, M. E. (1998). *Competitive strategy. Technique for analyzing industries and competitors*. the free press.
- Porter, M. E. (2006). *Competitive strategy: techniques for analyzing industries and competitors*, New York: Free Press.
- Reuben, J (2018). Diversification as a corporate strategy and its effect on firm performance: A Study of Zimbabwean Listed Conglomerates in the Food and Beverage Sector. *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 6(5), 182-195

- Quinn, J. B., Mintzberg, H., & James, R. M. (2019). The strategy process: concepts, contexts, and cases (p. 33). Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Sekaran, U. & Bougie, R. (2018). Research methods for business: a skill-building approach. 7th Edition, Wiley & Sons, West Sussex.
- Sidi, B.A., Haim, H., & Abdul Manaf, B (2020). Conceptualizing growth strategy on some performance in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research in Management*, 7(2), 30-41.
- Singh, S. K., Gupta, S., Busso, D., & Kamboj, S. (2021). Top management knowledge value, knowledge sharing practices, open innovation and organizational performance. *Journal of Business Research*, 128 (1), 788-798.
- SMEDAN (2012). Small and medium enterprises performance in Nigeria: A report presented at African entrepreneurship seminar organized in collaboration with the Scientific Committee on Entrepreneurship of the University of Essex. United Kingdom on the 5th of June State. *Economics of Development*, 17, 39-53.
- Uchegbulam, P., Akinyele, S., & Ibidunni, A. (2022). Competitive strategy and performance of selected SMEs in Nigeria. In *International Conference on African Development Issues: Social and Economic Models for Development Track* (pp. 326–333).
- Wang, C.-H. (2019). How organizational green culture influences green performance and competitive advantage. *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, 30(4), 666–683.
- Wang, G., Dou, W., Zhu, W., & Zhou, N. (2022). The effects of firm capabilities on external collaboration and performance: The moderating role of market turbulence. *Journal of Business Research*. 1(2), 11-34
- Warugu. E (2021). Market penetration strategies and organizational growth: A Case of soft drink sector in Kenya. *International Journal of Management and Commerce Innovations*, 3(2), 219-227
- Washington, P. (2024). Competitive intelligence practices and performance of firms listed on the Nairobi Securities Exchange, Kenya. *European Scientific Journal*. 1(2), 23-45
- Yogo, B. (2023). A resource-based view of the firm. *Strategic Management Journal*, 5(2), 171- 180
- Yusuf, A (2023). *Innovative east asia: the future of growth*, washington, D. C.: The World Bank, a Co-publication of the World Bank and Oxford University Press.

Zheng, H. (2022). SME strategic management and innovation a comparative study between Finland and China, pp. 1-16.